

ACADEMIC SELF-CONCEPT AND MOTIVATION AS PREDICTORS OF STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN MATHEMATICS

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Academic Self-Concept and Motivation as Predictors of Students' Achievement in Mathematics

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the relationship and predictive power of academic self-concept and motivation to tertiary students' Mathematics achievement. This descriptive correlational research was conducted with 347 college students in selected tertiary schools in Davao de Oro. Mean scores, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, and linear regression analysis were utilized to analyze the data. The study's result revealed that the students' academic self-concept is moderate, and their learning motivation is high. The study also reported a very satisfactory level of performance in Mathematics. Further, academic self-concept and motivation significantly predict students' mathematics achievement in Mathematics. These findings suggest that academic self-concept and motivation are vital factors in enhancing students' achievement in Mathematics. This study recommended integrating academic self-concept and motivation to amplify students' achievement in Mathematics, promoting a comprehensive approach to learning success.

Keywords: *mathematics education, academic self-concept, motivation, mathematics achievement*

Introduction

Education comprises many disciplines that every human should be taught and equipped with. Mathematics is one of the most well-established disciplines in every education curriculum (Guinocor et al., 2020). Mathematics is viewed as difficult, and it entails enough time and dedication to learn (Evarado & Itaas, 2024). Thus, students should dedicate significant time to their studies to graduate with high academic standing (Tadese et al., 2022). The study is motivated by the recognized challenges that students, especially in higher education, encounter in mastering this subject, acknowledging the significance of academic excellence, particularly in mathematics, as a foundation discipline. Existing literature reveals a global concern with low academic achievement in mathematics across nations, as indicated by studies such as those conducted by Tadese et al. (2022) and Guinocor et al. (2020).

Self-Determination Theory (SDT), elucidated by Ryan and Deci (2000), emphasizes the qualitative dimensions of motivation and delineates a continuum encompassing various motivational types. SDT, functioning as a metatheory for human development, emotions, and education, investigates the impact of social contexts and individual differences on autonomous and controlled motivation. In mathematics achievement, SDT underscores the importance of cultivating intrinsic motivation (Wright, 2015). Positive learning outcomes ensue when students experience autonomy and personal relevance in mathematical pursuits. Integrating SDT principles into educational strategies can enhance students' motivation and contribute to improved mathematics achievement (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Wright, 2015).

The study's independent variable, Academic self-concept, aligns with Shavelson's Hierarchical Model of Self-Concept, initially presented by Shavelson, Hubner, and Staton in 1976. This model delineates self-concept, with the latter specifying disciplines like mathematics and English (Ajmal & Rafique, 2018). Shavelson's widely acclaimed model served as a foundational framework for many others, emphasizing critical aspects of self-concept. Hence, believing in one's talents and perceiving strengths and capabilities impact academic success (Ajmal & Rafique, 2018). Thus, this underscores the interconnectedness of students' abilities and the strength of their self-concept in determining educational achievement.

The research is grounded in the Expectancy-Value Theory of achievement motivation, which posits a crucial role for self-concept and motivation in predicting student success. Developed by Eccles and her colleagues, this theory emphasizes that positive self-perception and interest in academic tasks heightened attention and adaptability, ultimately enhancing academic achievement (Cai et al., 2018). According to Eccles et al. (2000), the theory's subjective values, including attainment value, intrinsic value, utility value, and cost, highlight the importance of students' perceptions and attitudes. Interest value aligns with intrinsic motivation, emphasizing task engagement for interest and enjoyment, while utility value captures more extrinsic motivations tied to specific goals (Eccles, 2000; Deci & Ryan, 1985). The expectancy-value model considers factors influencing motivation, such as expectations for success and task value, including children's traits (skills, prior experiences, goals, self-concepts, beliefs, expectations, and interpretations) and environmental influences. It underscores the interconnectedness of self-concept, motivation, and student achievement, providing a comprehensive framework in predicting academic success.

Several research investigations on mathematics achievement among students have been conducted over the years, many focusing on self-concept and motivation as predictors of students' mathematics achievement. These studies have advanced the understanding of the variables that affect mathematics students' achievement and have suggested several methods for increasing student performance.

Research Questions

The study's main objective is to evaluate how academic self-concept and motivation affect students' academic achievement in

mathematics. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of students' academic self-concept in mathematics in terms of their:
 - 1.1. academic confidence; and
 - 1.2. academic effort?
2. What is the level of students' motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic regulation;
 - 2.2. amotivation;
 - 2.3. external regulation; and
 - 2.4. introjected regulation?
3. What is the Level of Students' Achievement in Mathematics?
4. Is there a significant relationship between academic self-concept and academic achievement of students in mathematics?
5. Is there a significant relationship between motivation and academic achievement of students in mathematics?
6. Which domain of academic self-concept significantly predicts the academic achievement of students in mathematics?
7. Which domain of motivation significantly predicts the academic achievement of students in mathematics?
8. Is academic self-concept and motivation predict students' academic achievement in mathematics?

Literature Review

A specific focus is directed towards Indonesia and the Philippines, where recent assessments, such as TIMMS (2019) and PISA (2018), underscore alarmingly low scores in mathematics (Mullis et al., 2020). The Philippines, in particular, ranks last in reading proficiency and second-to-last in mathematics among 79 OECD member and partner nations. Localized investigations at a state college in the Province of Davao De Oro further highlight student performance fluctuations over two academic years. The performance analysis for academic years 2021-2022 and 2020-2021 reveals noteworthy trends. In 2021-2022, 19.5% of students achieved outstanding performance, a significant increase from the previous year's 0.9%. The majority, 54.4%, attained a very satisfactory level, while 24.7% received a satisfactory rating. Remarkably, no students fell into the "did not meet expectation" category, contrasting with the concerning 21.5% in 2020-2021. Although the number of outstanding performers rose, fluctuations occurred in other categories, emphasizing the need to explore factors influencing the dynamics behind previous low performance, with a significant proportion not meeting expectations in the previous year, necessitating a deeper exploration.

Interestingly, research has shown that self-concept and academic achievement are highly correlated because students with strong self-expectations may impact their academic achievement (Koshkouei et al., 2016). Students with high academic self-concept also possess an excellent ability to solve mathematical test problems and vice versa (Fadillah et al., 2017). As cited in the study by Tan (2019), the research indicates that a strong academic self-concept and extensive use of learning strategies when solving mathematical problems would result in a high level of mathematical students' performance. Moreover, the study conducted by Gachigi (2018) showed that academic self-concept positively and significantly predicted mathematics achievement. Recebido (2022) explored the correlation between self-concept and senior high school students' math performance, involving 119 students in Sorsogon. The study suggests fostering a positive math self-concept and boosting math performance. Another study by Carrillo-López et al. (2022) underscores the crucial role of self-concept in predicting academic success, especially in core subjects like mathematics. The meta-analysis by Dulay (2017) reinforces the reciprocal link between self-concept and student achievement, advocating for educators to prioritize enhancing students' self-concept for improved academic outcomes. Deveci (2018) notes high academic self-concept and lifelong learning inclination as indicators of strong potential for academic success.

Furthermore, motivation plays a pivotal role as a catalyst for effort and achievement, with strong motivation for learning correlating with successful outcomes. According to study of Gachigi's (2018), selecting 500 participants through stratified random sampling, revealed a robust connection between academic motivation and mathematical achievement across various categories. Ariani (2016) explored 326 business and economics student, establishing academic motivation as a significant predictor of both behavioral control during learning and academic performance. Bailey and Phillips (2016), examining 184 first-year university students, found intrinsic motivation linked to greater subjective well-being, life purpose, and academic success, while amotivation consistently related to poorer outcomes. Extrinsically motivated students displayed limited connections to outcome variables. Berestova et al.'s (2022) survey involving 520 students from Russian and Bulgarian universities unveiled self-development, cognitive, achievement and self-esteem motivation as prevalent. The rejection of the null hypothesis indicated a difference in critical thinking outcomes between students with common types of academic motivation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive correlational studies describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them (Sousa et al., 2007). The design is appropriate since one of the purposes of the study was to identify the level and association between student academic self-concept and motivation level to the performance in the subject and to identify which of the following variables predicts Mathematics achievement.

Participants

The research was conducted at the identified four campuses of state colleges in the province of Davao de Oro, specifically in Compostela, New Bataan, Maragusan, and Montevista. Hence, the research chose this college since it offers teacher education courses, specifically the GED 3 subject (Mathematics in the Modern World). The study population consisted of first-year college students from all TEIs in Davao de Oro's chosen towns who are currently enrolled in GED 3 (Mathematics in the Modern World). Two thousand one hundred forty-one (2 141) first-year students. Respondents were selected using a simple random sampling method. Using Slovin's formula, the study's respondents are 336 and were divided among the four campuses, totaling 336 respondents of this study, comprising 148 respondents from Compostela, 70 respondents from Montevista, 68 respondents from Maragusan, and 50 respondents from New Bataan, respectively.

<i>Campus</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>
Compostela	148
Montevista	70
Maragusan	68
New Bataan	50
Total	336

Instruments

This study incorporated two existing questionnaires and one questionnaire developed by the researcher to assess the predictive levels of identified factors on students' academic achievement in Mathematics. The first questionnaire utilized was the Academic Self-Concept Scale (ASC). The Academic Self-Concept Scale is the initial survey instrument to be used. Liu and Wang (2005) developed the instrument's components, which included two subscales with a total of 10 items each: (a) academic confidence and (b) academic effort. In this study, a 20-item questionnaire with identified endpoints of strongly agree and strongly disagree and a 5-point Likert scale was used. To prevent repeat responses from the students, the items were worded both negatively and positively. A 5-point Likert scale—the parameters of the first independent variable—will serve as the parameter limit for the researcher's interpretation of the data.

On the other hand, to measure students' level of motivation toward their performance in Mathematics, the Academic Motivation Scale (AMS) developed by Vallerand et al., (1992, 1993) was utilized. The instrument's components, which included amotivation, external regulation, introjected regulation, identified regulation, and intrinsic motivation through five subscales.

The AMS was first back-translated into English by a graduate student who is proficient in both Italian and English before being translated into Italian by the authors. Then, impartial judges evaluated whether the scales and measures in the original and the back-translated versions were equivalent. The final editing was carried out following a discussion of instances of nonequivalence. The parameters of the second independent variable will determine the limit for the researcher's interpretation of the data.

Lastly, a questionnaire developed by researcher was utilized as the assessment tool, specifically serving as the final examination for the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024 for the general mathematics subject or the GED 3 (Mathematics in the Modern World) at the institution. The purpose of this questionnaire was to measure students' mathematics achievement by analyzing their scores on the aforementioned examination. The parameter limit provided below was utilized as a reference in evaluating and interpreting the students' test results. To ensure consistency and alignment with educational guidelines, the descriptors used to interpret the students' test results were adapted from DepEd Order No. 26, s. 2016.

The questionnaires, that were modified and utilized from recent research, have been validated. The researcher assessed its consistency and reliability by administering a pilot testing test to students who were not involved in the study.

Procedure

The following stages will be considered as data collection for the study conducted. Before the data collection, UMERC reviewed the ethical considerations of the study to guarantee that there would be no potential violations during the study's conduct. Data collection began after the UMERC gave their consent. The researcher will obtain a letter from the dean of graduate studies authorizing and certifying the research, which will serve as official documentation that U.M. Tagum College has approved the research. The organization's employer or agency will, after that, receive the letter of certification. After getting permission from the organization's employer or agency, the researcher will personally deliver the questionnaire to each respondent. The first-year Davao de Oro State College students will receive the questionnaire during the distribution process. The questionnaire included a short introduction, including instructions on how to answer the questionnaire to give proper education to the respondents to complete the survey.

To ensure no significant interruptions in their classes, the researcher arranged the data collection with the program head of each department of the different campuses since the students' classes' schedules differ. Moreover, informed student Consent was also provided to the students and retrieved by the researcher before the questionnaire was administered. The researcher also gave an orientation session regarding the study (purpose and process) to the involved students so that they would be aware of the purpose of this endeavor. There was also close coordination between the researcher, teacher/adviser of the students, and the program head to ensure that there would be no possible interruptions during data collection in the study's selected research locale. The researcher will

also give the respondents orientation and guidance to help them complete the questionnaires. This is to guarantee complete correctness in the questionnaire responses. The required tool must be tabulated, and the collected data must be analyzed and interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the conduct of the researcher's study, ethical issues and concerns may arise. It will ascertain that ethical standards would be strictly followed concerning protocol and standardized criteria, mainly managing the population and data such as, but not limited to the following:

Voluntary Participation. The participation of the respondents was purely voluntary. They will receive an informed consent form that will prove their agreement to participate as respondents in the study. In addition, they were well-versed in the nature and goal of the data gathering, including the risks and safeguards involved, which means that the information concerning personal data processes should be easy to access and easily understood using words and sentences within the subjects' comprehension. Furthermore, the data gathered will only be appropriate concerning the declared and specified purpose of the study. As such, the students may extract their selves as respondents without consequence.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Personal information was collected as part of the questionnaires, including personal information such as their basic demographic profiles (sex and email address), year, or grade level. The data gathered will be strictly used only for research and not for commercial purposes.

In connection, the processing of personal data will be allowed but subject to transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality, which signified that the researcher informed them on the purpose and processing of information relevant and not excessive concerning the specified purpose, the collection, processing, and retention of data gathered in the study adhered to the principles set by the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Section 19 of Rule IV stipulates that the collection of personal data must be (a) specified and has a legitimate purpose. The students will be given specific information regarding the purpose and extent of processing the data they provided and collected personal data necessary for the study. (b) Processed fairly means the researcher upheld the respondents' rights; this includes the right to refuse, withdraw consent, or object. The information given to the subjects will be understandable, clear, and in plain language. (c) Accurate- personal data were correct. Inaccurate data will be rectified or destroyed and restricted from further processing. (e) Not be retained longer than necessary- personal data were disposed of or discarded securely restricted from further processing, unauthorized access, or disclosure to other parties.

Falsification. The researcher will carefully examine the potential misinterpretation and analysis with the help of the assigned statistician and grammarian to maintain integrity and avoid any form of bias, such as changing the data to meet the desired study expectation.

Deceit. The researcher will briefly introduce the survey questionnaire, informing the learners of the title purpose, and give their rights as the study respondents to avoid any forms of misinformation.

Informed Consent Process. The Informed Consent Forms will be drafted following the guidelines set by the University of Mindanao, which align and comply with the requirements of the rules and regulations provided by the Data Privacy Act. The process of disseminating the Informed Consent Forms will involve a general orientation face-to-face before the conduct of the study, an explanation of the content of the Informed Consent Forms, and provide hard copies of the Inform Concept Form.

Risks. During the study, the respondents might feel uncomfortable gathering the data. Thus, the researcher will be sensitive to the student's feelings by ensuring that all questions and queries will be answered privately, meaning they could message the researcher privately. The students will not be forced in any way that might violate their well-being.

Benefits. The respondents' participation in this study would benefit students because the outcome could be the foundation of the intervention plans and programs that would help alleviate students' level of preparedness in learning on different platforms, especially the use of hybrid learning in case the situation needs to be addressed. This will serve as a springboard to identify potential instructional and intervention plans for teaching-learning.

Additionally, to avoid burdening the respondents in terms of accessibility to the internet connection, they were given a 15-peso load credit for their internet data needed to answer the survey. The researcher received no tangible benefits throughout the conduct of the study.

Recruitment. The researcher took into consideration the handling of the selection process of the respondents in an ethical manner. The respondents should not feel any pressure to answer the questionnaire, thus giving them ample time to think about their participation in the study. The researcher ensured that students' privacy was considered and dealt with accordingly and with the utmost respect. The respondents were given clear and unbiased information about what the study was all about. The researcher should avoid giving misleading information to lure the respondents about the survey. The researcher answered all queries of the respondents based on what was in the study.

Generally, during the recruitment stage, they were given precise data, able to understand the significance of their participation, which means that the researcher, who happens to be an instructor of the institution, laid down the importance of the study and were informed of the required or expected time duration of the study. The researcher announced to the respondents the nature of the questionnaire and

how it was to be answered.

Plagiarism. To ensure that study is written originally by the researcher, there would be an external body to check, monitor, and identify the potential plagiarism committed by the researcher. The editors used software such as Grammarly and Turnitin to check the possibility of plagiarism.

Fabrication. To ensure that the data presented in the study is appropriate and correct, a statistician assigned by the institution served as the sole analyst of the study.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher, who holds a full-time teaching position at one of the participating institutions, acknowledges the potential for a conflict of interest in approving and conducting the study. This conflict of interest may arise if the researcher has pre-existing personal relationships or familiarity with the subjects or facilitators involved in the study. To ensure the highest ethical standards are maintained, the researcher will diligently disclose any potential conflicts of interest to the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) for thorough consideration.

When the researcher is acquainted with the subjects or facilitators, it becomes even more crucial to address any potential conflicts of interest. The disclosure process plays a vital role in this regard. The researcher will provide a comprehensive account of any personal connections or affiliations to the UMERC, explicitly outlining the nature and extent of these relationships. This disclosure aims to promote transparency, integrity, and objectivity in the study. The disclosure of potential conflicts of interest will be carried out with utmost care and professionalism. The researcher will share all relevant details with the UMERC, ensuring the confidentiality of sensitive information. By disclosing the researcher's associations, the UMERC can make an informed judgment regarding any potential biases or compromises to the study's validity.

The UMERC, as an impartial body, will critically evaluate the disclosed information and consider it alongside other ethical considerations. Their primary goal will be to safeguard the study's integrity and minimize any undue influence. In situations where the UMERC determines that the researcher's conflict of interest poses a significant risk to the study's objectivity, appropriate measures will be implemented. These measures may include implementing safeguards such as independent oversight of the research process, excluding the researcher from certain aspects of the study, or any other necessary actions to mitigate the conflict of interest. The UMERC's involvement ensures an unbiased evaluation and decision-making process, reinforcing the credibility and reliability of the study's findings.

Permission from Organization/ Location. Before data collection, UMERC will review the ethical considerations of the study to guarantee that there will be no potential violations in the conduct of the study. Data collection will begin after the UMERC gives consent. After the UMERC's approval for the study's conduct, the researcher will seek permission from the Davao de Oro State College through the Office of the College President. Once the approval is secured, the researcher will be sending the permission letters to the college's Director of Academic Affairs. The questionnaire will include a short introduction, including instructions on how to answer the questionnaire to give proper education to the respondents to complete the survey.

Authorship. The researcher was a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics at Compostela Valley State College, Main Campus-Compostela. The researcher is currently studying for a Master of Arts in Education major in Teaching Mathematics and conducting a study about academic self-concept and motivation as predictors of students' achievement in mathematics. In addition, this manuscript underwent a series of modifications and revisions to improve the different essential elements of the research, such as but not limited to the research method, research design, and statistical tool to be used in the study.

It is noteworthy to mention that the researcher's adviser, who will also serve as her co-researcher for this study, possesses relevant expertise in the field. The adviser is an experienced educator with a distinguished career in mathematics education. Their extensive knowledge and experience in the subject matter will greatly contribute to the research's quality and insights.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the study's findings, analysis, and intervention implications. The data is conveyed through tabular and textual formats and thoroughly examined and interpreted all inferential results at a significance threshold of 0.05. Tables and their interpretations were organized chronologically under the following headings: level of students' academic self-concept, level of students' motivation, level of students' mathematics achievement, the significant relationship of the student's academic self-concept and motivation to student's mathematics achievement, and regression analysis on the following variables. This indicates that the completed questionnaire's evaluations are close to the mean, signifying that the respondents' responses on all items are consistent. The following discussions below are the results of the analysis organized and discussed according to the study's objectives.

Level of Students' Academic Self-Concept

Table 1 illustrates the overall academic self-concept, with moderate mean scores for academic effort and confidence. This suggests that students in the study generally had a moderate level of academic self-concept. These findings underscore the importance of addressing factors influencing self-concept to potentially enhance overall academic achievement.

Table 1. *Level of Academic Self-Concept*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Academic Effort	3.12	0.54	Moderate
Academic Confidence	3.20	0.53	Moderate
Overall	3.16	0.47	Moderate

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00, Very High; 3.40 – 4.19, High; 2.60 – 3.39, Moderate; 1.80 – 2.59, Low; 1.00 – 1.79, Very Low

The data in appended Table 1 reveals that the respondents observed the following order of priority for academic confidence: item 3 has the highest mean score which reveals that there is a high level of belief among students that diligent effort and hard work significantly contribute to achieving favorable grades. This positive correlation between hard work and academic success could be leveraged in educational interventions, emphasizing the importance of a strong work ethic. Next, item 6 which reveals a high level of confidence in the ability to retain and apply learned material effectively. This suggests that students may benefit from instructional strategies that focus on practical application and real-world scenarios, reinforcing their confidence in the practical utility of academic knowledge. Moderate levels were observed in the item, and no other aspects were observed, such as excelling in coursework and tests. These moderate levels indicate areas where targeted support and encouragement may be beneficial. Implementing interventions that foster a positive learning environment and provide constructive feedback could increase confidence in their domains.

Interestingly, items such as following lectures (item 1), helping classmates with schoolwork (item 2), and self-perceived intelligence compared to classmates (item 4) received relatively lower mean score, suggesting a need for focused attention. Strategies to enhance student engagement during lectures, promote collaborative learning, and foster a growth mindset could positively impact confidence in this area.

Moreover, the details in Table 1 sheds valuable insights into the priorities and attitudes of respondents regarding academic effort. Notably, students express a high level of attention during lectures (item 3), suggesting a keen interest in the classroom learning environment. This emphasis on attentiveness allows educators to capitalize on interactive teaching methods and dynamic presentations to engage students further. Additionally, the moderate level of determination and persistence when faced with difficult questions (item 9) underscores a commendable resilience among students. Educational interventions could focus on providing support mechanisms and resilience-building activities, encouraging students to persevere through challenging academic situations. Moreover, the moderate level of interest in coursework (item 5) indicates an openness to engagement. Educators might consider incorporating real-world applications, interactive projects, or practical examples that align with students' curiosity, further cultivating their intrinsic interest in the subject matter.

However, the data indicates areas of potential improvement, such as moderate anticipation to complete lectures (item 8) and motivation to persevere and excel in the course subject (item 7). These aspects call for pedagogical strategies that sustain interest throughout lectures and foster a sense of purpose and connection to the course subject. Lastly, the moderate level of commitment to studying hard for tests (item 4) signals an opportunity for interventions to develop effective study habits and emphasize the importance of consistent preparation.

This finding is similar to the study of Dulay (2017), which indicates a moderate positive effect of self-concept on student achievement, emphasizing the significance of self-concept in predicting and enhancing academic achievement. Jaiswal and Choudhuri (2017) contribute to this understanding by establishing that students generally possess an average level of academic self-concept, with higher self-concepts correlating positively with academic achievement. Thus, students with well-developed self-regulation skills are more likely to invest effort in their academic studies (Deveci, 2018).

Additionally, Watson et al. (2019) note the emergence of subject-specific self-concepts, influencing cognitive development and enthusiasm for learning. The research underscores the impact of ambition and self-expectations on academic achievement (Koshkouei et al., 2016), with positive academic self-concepts correlating with improved problem-solving abilities in mathematics (Fadillah et al., 2017). Moreover, Recebido's (2022) study emphasizes the role of teachers in fostering positive self-concepts, particularly in mathematics, as higher self-concept levels correspond to better performance in the subject. Hence, the cumulative evidence highlights the interconnectedness of self-concept and academic achievement, emphasizing the crucial role of educators in cultivating positive self-perceptions to enhance students' overall success.

Level of Students' Motivation in Mathematics

Table 2 reveals an overall positive mean score for students' motivation in Mathematics. Notably, the moderate level of amotivation underscores a degree of disinterest, urging educators to delve into potential root causes such as curriculum relevance or instructional strategies to reignite enthusiasm. Meanwhile, the high levels of external and introjected regulations suggest strong external influences and internal pressures. Strategies promoting intrinsic motivation should be integrated to balance these external factors, fostering sustained engagement. The moderate level of identified regulation implies that while students recognize mathematics importance, internalization is incomplete. Educators can enhance identified regulation by illustrating practical applications and aligning the subject with students' personal goals. Lastly, the high level of intrinsic regulation is promising, signifying internal motivation rooted in genuine interest. Capitalizing on this intrinsic motivation through challenging tasks and a positive learning environment can further elevate engagement and learning outcomes.

Table 2. *Level of Motivation*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Amotivation	3.71	0.89	High
External Regulation	3.75	0.83	High
Introjected Regulation	3.68	0.86	High
Identified Regulation	3.34	0.89	Moderate
Intrinsic Regulation	3.74	1.00	High
Overall Mean	3.65	0.76	High

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00, Very High; 3.40 – 4.19, High; 2.60 – 3.39, Moderate; 1.80 – 2.59, Low; 1.00 – 1.79, Very Low

The data appended reveals distinct areas of positive perception among students regarding amotivation. The high confidence expressed in understanding the benefits of attending school (item 3) suggests that students acknowledge the value of education, allowing educators to reinforce this positive attitude through practical demonstrations of the benefit of learning. Additionally, the reported high eagerness to embrace school opportunities (item 5) indicates a readiness for involvement, providing educators with a cue to create a stimulating and participatory learning environment that aligns with students' enthusiasm. The high level of confidence in understanding tasks and activities (item 4) offers a foundation for educators to introduce more challenging tasks, fostering a sense of competence and achievement.

Furthermore, the high confidence that time spent in school is valuable (item 1) underscore a positive outlook on the educational experience, suggesting a need for activities that emphasize the practical application and relevance of the curriculum. Lastly, the high confidence in students' reasons for attending school (item 2) emphasizes the importance of understanding individual motivations. Educators can tailor interventions to align with these motivations, ensuring that the school experience resonates with students' personal goals and aspirations.

Table 2 unveils distinct priorities among students regarding external regulations, shedding light on their motivation shaped by various factors. Item 4 has the highest mean, a strong motivation driven by the aspiration to have "the good life" in the future. This underscores the significance of discussing future goals in academic discourse, potentially enhancing intrinsic motivation. Additionally, item 5 suggests strong adherence to doing homework based on rules, highlighting the positive influence of external regulations on student discipline. The desire for a better salary later on (item 3) underscores pronounced external motivation tied to financial goals. Educators can reinforce the practical benefits of education in securing future economic stability.

Furthermore, the high level of motivation expressed in item 1, believing that a college diploma is necessary for a high-paying job, emphasizes the perceived importance of higher education. Reinforcing the link between education and career opportunities could positively impact students' motivation and commitment to academic pursuits. These insights provide educators with specific areas to address when designing interventions to enhance overall student motivation aligned with external regulations.

Table 2 outlines the respondents' priorities concerning introjected regulation, highlighting distinct motivational factors. Item 1 suggests a high level of confidence in one's capabilities to complete a college degree successfully. This finding underscores the importance of fostering self-efficacy beliefs, potentially contributing to sustained academic commitment. Similarly, item 4 reflects high confidence in the belief that success is achievable in academic studies. Educators can capitalize on this positive perception to reinforce a sense of competence and mastery in students' academic endeavors. Additionally, item 5 indicates that students express high motivation when working on classwork to be perceived as good students by the teacher. Acknowledging and appreciating students' efforts to meet teacher expectations can contribute to positive reinforcement and sustained motivation. Item 2 suggests that students perceived a sense of importance tied to their success in school.

This finding underscores the need for educators to recognize and reinforce the intrinsic value students attach to academic achievement, potentially enhancing their overall motivation. On the other hand, item 3 indicates a slightly lower level of confidence in considering oneself as an intelligent person. Addressing and positively influencing students' self-perceptions of intelligence is crucial to fostering a more confident and empowered approach to learning. These nuanced insights provide education with specific areas to target when designing interventions that consider students' perceptions of importance and intelligence in the academic context.

Table 2 provides insights into the prioritization of identified regulations among respondents. Item 1 indicates high motivation as students recognize the importance of success in school for making better career decisions, highlighting the need for educators to emphasize this connection in their teaching to sustain student motivation. Item 4 reflects high motivation as students believe their college education will enhance their competence as workers. This finding emphasizes the perceived value of education in developing practical skills, suggesting that educators can improve motivation by integrating real-world applications into the curriculum. Furthermore, item 3 reveals high motivation in believing that a college education will better prepare students for their chosen careers. Educators can leverage this motivation by aligning academic content with practical career relevance, reinforcing the value of education in achieving professional goals. Item 5 highlights high motivation associated with the inclination to do homework to understand the subject matter. This implies that reinforcing the intrinsic value of understanding the material can positively impact student engagement in academic tasks. Lastly, item 2 shows a high motivation associated with the belief that success in school enables entry into the job market in a preferred field. Educators can capitalize on this motivation by emphasizing the long-term benefits of academic success in securing desired career paths.

Lastly, Table 2 outlines the priorities for intrinsic regulation among respondents. Item 3 indicates a high level of enjoyment in doing classwork, suggesting intrinsic satisfaction with academic tasks. This emphasizes the importance of creating a positive and engaging learning environment that fosters enjoyment in the learning process. Item 5 is associated with a high level of intrinsic motivation linked to the experience of broadening knowledge about subjects that appeal to students. This finding underscores the significance of offering diverse and interesting subjects that align with students' interests to enhance intrinsic motivation.

Similarly, item 4 reveals high intrinsic motivation as students believe their studies allow them to continue learning about many interesting things. Educators can leverage this intrinsic motivation by incorporating varied and engaging learning materials that cater to individual interests. Item 2 indicates high intrinsic motivation as students experience and discover new things in the learning process. Hands-on and exploratory learning approaches can enhance intrinsic motivation by providing students with opportunities for discovery. Lastly, item 1 highlights a high level of intrinsic motivation observed with students reporting pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things. This emphasizes the emotional aspects of learning and the importance of creating a positive and effective connection to academic tasks.

Similar findings to the study of Kriegbaum and Spinath (2018) claim that motivated students are more likely to set challenging goals, have higher self-efficacy, and exhibit adaptive learning strategies, all contributing to academic success. Moreover, according to research conducted by Sotos-Martínez et al. (2023), motivation directly impacts students' achievement by influencing their engagement, effort, and persistence in various academic tasks. Furthermore, Fomina (2018) found that motivated students are more inclined to set challenging goals, exert additional effort, and persist in facing obstacles, ultimately leading to higher academic achievement. Motivation plays a significant and distinctive role in predicting academic success, substantially contributing to students' cognitive processes, including attention, memory, and problem-solving skills. This, in turn, results in an enhancement of overall academic performance.

Level of Students' Achievement in Mathematics

The distribution of scores in Table 3 provides valuable insights into students' performance in the assessment, offering a nuanced perspective on their achievements across different score ranges. Notably, the highest score range indicates exceptional performance. The highest category, designated as "Outstanding," implies that a noteworthy proportion of students demonstrated superior performance, signaling the presence of academic excellence within the cohort. This insight has positive implications for recognizing and cultivating exceptional talent, possibly through enrichment programs or advanced coursework. The prevalence of the "Very Satisfactory" category, which constitutes the majority of students, suggests a widespread high level of competence and accomplishment. This trend in the data implies a positive overall academic performance among a significant portion of the student population. The discussion around this category could involve exploring teaching methods, curriculum effectiveness, or identifying areas for continuous improvement to maintain this positive trajectory.

Table 3. *Level of Achievement in Mathematics*

Score	f	Percentage	Description
41 – 50	46	13.3%	Outstanding
31 – 40	174	50.14%	Very Satisfactory
21 – 30	126	36.31%	Satisfactory
11 – 20	1	0.29%	Fairly Satisfactory
1 – 10	0	0%	Did Meet Expectations
Overall Mean		32.76	Very Satisfactory

The distribution of scores in Table 3 provides valuable insights into students' performance in the assessment, offering a nuanced perspective on their achievements across different score ranges. Notably, the highest score range indicates exceptional performance. The highest category, designated as "Outstanding," implies that a noteworthy proportion of students demonstrated superior performance, signaling the presence of academic excellence within the cohort. This insight has positive implications for recognizing and cultivating exceptional talent, possibly through enrichment programs or advanced coursework. The prevalence of the "Very Satisfactory" category, which constitutes the majority of students, suggests a widespread high level of competence and accomplishment. This trend in the data implies a positive overall academic performance among a significant portion of the student population. The discussion around this category could involve exploring teaching methods, curriculum effectiveness, or identifying areas for continuous improvement to maintain this positive trajectory.

The "Satisfactory" category, although not reaching the highest level of achievement, indicates a solid performance level among many students. The discussion here may focus on understanding factors contributing to the range, identifying areas for improvement, and tailoring interventions to enhance student outcomes within this category further. The absence of instances in the lowest category, labeled "Did Not Meet Expectations," is a positive outcome, indicating that no students fell below the expected performance level. This absence suggests that the student population generally met the academic expectations set for the assessment. The discussion around this absence might involve reflecting on the effectiveness of instructional strategies and assessment design.

The alignment of the overall mean score with the category labeled "Very Satisfactory" indicates that, on average, students performed

well within high competence and achievement expectations. This alignment provides a comprehensive overview of the collective academic performance and reinforces the overall success of the student cohort. The discussion could delve into the factors contributing to this alignment and how they can be sustained or enhanced.

This finding is supported by Ayebale et al. (2020), who assert its pervasive influence across diverse aspects of human life. Their research emphasizes the multifaceted nature of factors impacting students' achievement in mathematics, encompassing teaching methods, teachers' attitudes, and students' perceptions. Furthermore, Ayebale et al. (2020) underscore the crucial role of enjoyment and attitudes as predictors of students' performance in the subject. This aligns with Mazana et al. (2019), who delve into the nuanced factors influencing students' preferences for or aversions to mathematics, identifying aptitude attributes, instructional practices, and social-psychological environments as pivotal determinants. Together, these studies highlight the interconnectedness of academic and non-academic elements in shaping students' attitudes and, subsequently, their success in mathematics, advocating for holistic strategies to enhance the overall learning experience.

Significance of the Relationship between Academic Self-Concept and Students' Achievement in Mathematics

Presented in Table 4 is the significance between academic self-concept and students' achievement in Mathematics. The hypotheses were tested using a 0.05 level of significance. Using the Pearson-r correlation test, the relationship between the independent and dependent variables was tested. To verify the relationship, the p-value indicated in the table suggests rejecting the null hypothesis. The correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between academic self-concept and students' achievement in mathematics. This result indicates that academic self-concept increases, as does academic achievement in mathematics.

Moreover, the moderate positive coefficient of 0.056 suggests that as academic self-concept increases, achievement in mathematics tends to rise as well. The r^2 value is 0.256, indicating that when both academic effort and academic confidence are considered at once, they collectively explain about 25.6% of the variance in mathematics achievement among individuals in the sample. These findings support the hypothesis that higher levels of academic self-concept are associated with improved academic achievement.

Table 4. *Significance of the Relationship between Academic Self-Concept and Achievement in Mathematics*

<i>Independent Variable (Academic Self-Concept)</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Academic Effort	Achievement in Mathematics	0.488*	0.201	0.000	Reject H_0
Academic Confidence		0.400*	0.160	0.000	Reject H_0
Overall		0.506	0.256	0.000	Reject H_0

This is supported by the study conducted by Susperreguy et al. (2017), which reveals that individuals who have a positive self-concept of their mathematics abilities are more likely to perform better in mathematics. Self-concept refers to an individual's perception and belief about their competence in a specific domain, such as mathematics. It encompasses their confidence, beliefs, and attitudes toward their mathematics ability. Thus, self-concept in mathematics predicts later achievement in the subject. Further, in the study of Lee and Kung (2018), the researchers have found a significant relationship between math self-concept and academic achievement, including mathematics achievement. Studies have shown that students with higher self-concepts tend to have higher mathematics achievement. Thus, Self-concept theory suggests that self-concept is a multifaceted construct that includes academic self-concept, which relates to academic and scholastic activities. Academic self-concept varies based on subject domains, such as math or reading, and is related to current and future subject-specific achievement. (DeVries et al., 2021)

Significance of the Relationship between Motivation and Students' Achievement in Mathematics

Presented in Table 5 is the significance between motivation and students' achievement in mathematics. The hypotheses were tested using a 0.05 level of significance. The relationship between the independent and dependent variables was tested using the Pearson correlation test. The p-value presented in the table implies the rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, the correlation of 0.452 demonstrated a statistically moderate positive relationship between motivation and students' achievement in mathematics. This finding indicates that higher motivation levels are associated with better academic performance in mathematics. Thus, more motivated students tend to excel in their mathematical studies. Moreover, the r^2 value is 0.204, suggesting that approximately 20.4% of the mathematics achievement can be explained by considering all the indicators of motivation.

Table 5. *Significance of the Relationship between Motivation and Achievement in Mathematics*

<i>Independent Variable (Motivation)</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Amotivation	Achievement	0.365*	0.133	0.000	Reject H_0
External Regulation	in Mathematics	0.358*	0.128	0.000	Reject H_0
Introjected Regulation		0.344*	0.118	0.000	Reject H_0
Identified Regulation		0.433*	0.187	0.000	Reject H_0
Intrinsic Regulation		0.414*	0.171	0.000	Reject H_0
Overall		0.452	0.204	0.000	Reject H_0

The emphasis on motivation highlights the importance of fostering intrinsic motivation, an internal desire to engage in and master mathematical concepts. Educators should tailor instructional strategies to enhance and sustain students' motivation in mathematics. Implementing diverse and engaging teaching methods, incorporating real-world applications, and highlighting mathematical concepts' relevance can increase motivation. By implementing these strategies, educators can nurture motivation, making mathematics an engaging and meaningful pursuit for students.

This finding supports the study of Ning (2020), who highlighted the importance of promoting students' self-determined motivation in mathematics, as it can positively impact their academic achievement. Motivation is a driving force behind students' academic achievement, with perceived competence emerging as a more influential factor than task value, according to Prast et al. (2018). Particularly in mathematics, fostering motivation involves students taking ownership of their learning, setting goals, and maintaining autonomy. This connection between motivation and achievement establishes a mutually reinforcing cycle contributing to future success. Berestova et al. (2021) further highlight the significant impact of academic motivation, encompassing self-development, cognitive achievement, and self-esteem motivations, on students' mathematics achievement. El-Adl and Alkharusi's (2020) study reinforces the interconnected nature of self-regulated learning strategies, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, task value, and academic achievement. Fostering self-regulated learning skills can positively influence students' motivation, beliefs about learning control, self-efficacy, and, consequently, academic achievement. This insight informs educational practices, emphasizing the pivotal role of intrinsic motivation in enhancing students' performance in mathematics.

Regression Analysis Among Indicators of Academic Self-Concept as Predictor of Student's Achievement in Mathematics

Presented in Table 6 is the regression analysis among indicators of academic self-concept to students' achievement in mathematics. The regression analysis indicates that the indicators of academic self-concept, when considered together, can significantly account for variations in students' mathematics achievement. The moderate positive relationship and the coefficient of determination further emphasize the explanatory power of academic self-concept, explaining the variability in students' achievement in mathematics. Furthermore, the specific examination of academic confidence reveals its predictive value for academic effort; this suggests that students with higher levels of academic confidence and academic effort are more likely to achieve better results in mathematics. Moreover, the r^2 is 0.265, meaning that around 26.5% of the variability in mathematics achievement in the sample can be attributed to academic effort and confidence. Moreover, r -value of 0.514 indicates a moderate positive correlation. It suggests that changes in academic effort and confidence are associated with changes in achievement in Mathematics.

Table 6. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Academic Self-Concept to the Achievement in Mathematics

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	P-value	Decision
	β	Std. Error				
(constant)	12.587	1.877				
Academic Effort	4.236	0.605	0.384*	7.001	0.000	Reject H_0
Academic Confidence	2.179	0.616	0.194*	3.538	0.000	Reject H_0

Dependent Variable: Achievement in Mathematics

Note: $R = 0.514$; $R^2 = 0.265$; F -ratio = 61.884; P -value = 0.000

In practical terms, educators and policymakers may consider interventions that foster and enhance students' academic confidence, recognizing its potential impact on mathematics achievement. These insights could guide the development of targeted strategies to promote a positive academic self-concept among students, ultimately contributing to improved performance in mathematics. Additionally, while academic effort may be valuable for various aspects of learning, its limited significance in predicting math achievement in this context suggests a need for further exploration and understanding of the unique factors influencing success in mathematics education.

The moderate positive correlation coefficient of 0.514 suggests a discernible association between academic effort, academic confidence, and students' achievement in mathematics. This indicates that as academic effort and academic confidence increase, there tends to be a corresponding increase in achievement in mathematics. Additionally, the r^2 value of 0.265 signifies that approximately 26.5% of the variance in achievement in mathematics can be explained by academic effort and academic confidence.

The findings echo Granero-Gallegos et al.'s (2021) study, emphasizing the pivotal role of academic confidence and effort in shaping students' overall academic experience. Motivation and satisfaction diminishes when students lack confidence and exert insufficient effort in their academic pursuits, hindering effective studying. This aligns with the notion that individuals with high academic confidence and effort levels are more likely to succeed academically. Academic engagement is heightened when students believe they possess the necessary skills for school tasks, underscoring the importance of fostering academic effort for satisfaction, commitment, and eventual academic achievement.

Teachers contribute significantly to students' learning pleasure by creating a supportive and nurturing classroom environment. Allred and Cena (2020) emphasize the positive impact of integrating play, creativity, and exploration into lessons, fostering an environment where learning is associated with pleasure and success. This approach enhances students' self-concepts, leading to improved academic achievement. Moreover, the study by Gallegos et al. (2021) reinforces the interconnectedness of confidence, academic effort, motivation, and overall academic success, highlighting the need to cultivate these factors for a comprehensive and enriching academic

experience. These insights underscore the critical interplay between academic confidence, effort, and teacher-created learning environments in shaping students' academic commitment, engagement, and achievement.

Regression Analysis Among Indicators of Motivation as Predictor of Student's Achievement in Mathematics

Table 7. Regression Analysis on the Influence of Motivation to the Achievement in Mathematics

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value	Decision
	β	Std. Error	Beta			
(constant)	19.481	1.434				
Amotivation	-0.505	0.749	-0.076	-0.674	0.501	Failed to Reject H_0
External Regulation	0.610	0.681	0.085	0.896	0.371	Failed to Reject H_0
Introjected Regulation	0.224	0.650	0.032	0.346	0.730	Failed to Reject H_0
Identified Regulation	1.999	0.377	0.301*	5.308	0.000	Reject H_0
Intrinsic Regulation	1.431	0.476	0.242*	3.008	0.003	Reject H_0

Dependent Variable: Achievement in Mathematics

Note: $R = 0.495$; $R^2 = 0.245$; F -ratio = 22.080; P -value = 0.000

The regression analysis presented in Table 7 emphasizes the collective significance of motivation in predicting students' achievement in mathematics. The positive relationship between motivation and achievement underscores that motivation explains a substantial portion of the variability in mathematics achievement. Examining specific motivational aspects, identified regulation and intrinsic regulation emerge as key predictors of students' achievement in mathematics. Fostering these aspects could positively impact students' performance in the subject.

Conversely, the non-significant impact of introjected regulation, amotivation, and external regulation suggests that these particular motivational dimensions do not significantly predict mathematics achievement in this context. These findings have important implications for educational strategies and interventions. Prioritizing identified and intrinsic regulation in motivational interventions may improve students' mathematics achievement more effectively. Recognizing the distinct contributions of each motivational aspect allows for tailored approaches that align with the unique dynamics of student motivation, ultimately enhancing academic outcomes. A moderate positive correlation coefficient r value of 0.495 indicates a discernible association between motivation and academic achievement in mathematics. Furthermore, the r^2 value of 0.245 reveals that approximately 24.5% of the variance in achievement in mathematics can be explained by motivation factors; it also suggests that other variables not considered in the analysis may influence academic achievement.

These findings, supported by the study of Javadi and Faryabi (2016), indicated that intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors lacked a significant correlation with academic achievement. This suggests that students' intrinsic or extrinsic motivation level does not distinctly impact their academic success. The specificity of intrinsic and identified motivations, as opposed to the non-specificity of introjected and external motivations, highlights key considerations in school motivation research. Guay and Bureau (2018) emphasized that intrinsic and identified motivations have a subject-specific influence, significantly impacting achievement in specific subjects. In contrast, introjected and external regulations negatively relate to achievement across subjects. Howard et al. (2021) further underscored the importance of identified regulation and intrinsic motivation in school adjustments, emphasizing their positive correlation with performance, well-being, goal orientation, and persistence. Fostering intrinsic motivation and personal values is crucial for positive academic outcomes, suggesting a need for tailored interventions in school motivation practices.

Regression Analysis Among Indicators of Academic Self-Concept and Motivation as Predictor to Student's Achievement in Mathematics

Presented in Table 8 is the regression analysis among indicators of academic self-concept and motivation to students' achievement in mathematics, demonstrating a significant predictive relationship. A substantial F -ratio and low p -value support the collective impact of academic self-concept and motivation. This suggests that when considered together, these factors significantly contribute to predicting students' achievement in mathematics. A moderate positive correlation exists between academic self-concept, motivation, and achievement in mathematics. This suggests that there is a discernible association between students' perceptions of their academic abilities, their motivation levels, and their achievement in mathematics. Moreover, the r^2 value of 0.271 means that approximately 27.1% of the variance in achievement in mathematics can be explained by academic self-concept and motivation. Specifically, academic self-concept and

Table 8. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Academic Self-Concept and Motivation of Achievement in Mathematics

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-value	t-value	Decision
	β	Std. Error	Beta			
(constant)	12.574	1.867				
Academic Self-Concept	4.782	0.847	0.376*	0.000	5.647	Reject H_0
Motivation	1.395	0.518	0.179*	0.007	2.691	Reject H_0

Dependent Variable: Achievement in Mathematics

Note: $R = 0.512$; $R^2 = 0.271$; F -ratio = 64.097; P -value = 0.000

Motivation exhibits individual predictive power, as indicated by their respective beta values and p-values. The beta values underscore the importance of academic self-concept and motivation in predicting students' success in mathematics. These findings underscore the need for interventions and strategies that foster positive academic self-concept and motivation to enhance students' overall achievement in mathematics.

This is supported by the study of Obilor and Briggs (2021), which states that students' academic achievement is intricately linked to their self-concept, self-awareness, and self-motivation. Notably, mathematics self-efficacy emerged as a significant predictor, emphasizing the importance of students' belief in their ability to succeed in mathematical pursuits (Pitsia et al., 2017). A positive self-concept and heightened achievement motivation were vital contributors to academic success, indicating the potential impact of interventions targeting students' mathematics self-beliefs and attitudes toward learning (Obilor & Briggs, 2021). Furthermore, studies underscore the predictive power of self-concept, test anxiety, and academic motivation in secondary school students' achievement (Onukwufor & Ugwu, 2017).

Moreover, Surayanah and Karma's (2018) research adds depth, revealing the positive and significant impact of school climate, achievement motivation, and self-concept on student achievement. The combined effect of these factors suggests the need for a holistic approach involving teachers, parents, and students to create an optimal learning environment. Encouraging teacher support, parental involvement, and fostering a conducive school climate are vital to enhancing students' academic achievement (Surayanah & Karma, 2018; Onukwufor & Ugwu, 2017).

Conclusions

Based on the discussions, the researcher has concluded that academic self-concept is moderate and motivation is high. The study also recorded a very satisfactory level of students' achievement in mathematics. Moreover, the study showed that academic self-concept and motivation have a significant relationship to students' achievement in Mathematics and predict students' achievement in Mathematics. Furthermore, indicators of academic self-concept - academic effort and academic confidence, predict students' achievement in mathematics. Also, indicators of motivation such as identified regulation and intrinsic regulation predict students' achievement in Mathematics; on the other hand, indicators such as amotivation, extrinsic regulation, and introjected regulation have no predictive ability to achievement. However, when taken as a whole, motivation can predict students' achievement in Mathematics. Hence, academic self-concept and motivation can predict student achievement in Mathematics.

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